

DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF A SINGLE VOLUME INFLATABLE STRUCTURE SYSTEM FOR THE ICARUS INFLATABLE HEATSHIELD

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ABSTRACT

ICARUS is a project funded by the European Union's HORIZON EUROPE program under the grant agreement No 101134997. It targets to bring up to TRL6 the maturation of enabling technologies in the field of re-usable space transportation systems, addressing the innovative re-entry solution based on Inflatable Heat Shields, deemed applicable for recovery of Launch Vehicles stages.

This paper addresses the design and development of the Inflatable Structure and the associated Cool Gas Generator. An overview of a system featuring a single pressurized rotationally symmetric volume, inflated with the Cool Gas Generator, is presented. It is one of three key Inflatable Heat Shield technologies pursued in the ICARUS project, including the Flexible Thermal Protection System, and Health Monitoring Sensors. Orbital and suborbital demonstrations, as well as conceptualization of the Inflatable Heat Shield to date, employ designs with multiple separated Inflatable Structure volumes. These include stacked toroidal configurations or separate conical volumes with toroidal back shells. The aero shape is formed with stored high-pressure inflation gas post-launch separation and pre-atmospheric re-entry of a re-entry vehicle. The separated volumes, and the gas storage system are areas where further simplification is realized in the ICARUS aero-demonstration mission.

The cross-section around the axis of symmetry holds an inverse tear-drop shape with a toroidal back shell. The associated Cool Gas Generator, employing chemically stored gas in a solid state, produces pure gas at ambient temperature and relatively low pressures. Gas is released with a decomposition reaction. This innovative approach eliminates the need for high-pressure systems, reducing safety concerns at the launch site and minimizing additional qualification efforts. The interface and interaction of the Inflatable Structure to the Cool Gas Generator is investigated, having a two-stage inflation process at lower pressures first, and then higher pressures. To further support design decisions, a material selection

for the Inflatable Structure is defined. This is aimed to evaluate mechanical and thermal material characterization, as well as breadboard leakage and deflection testing of material combinations and manufacturing techniques. Results are supported with numerical simulations.

1. INTRODUCTION

ICARUS stands for Inflatable Concept Aero-shell for the Recovery of a re-Usable launcher Stage and is a European consortium aiming to develop an inflatable heat shield (IHS) to recover rocket stages and support future Mars missions [1]. The project brings together eleven partners under the coordination of Indra-Deimos, forming a full EU collaboration. ATMOS is responsible for the Inflatable Structure (IS) of the sub-orbital demonstrator mission planned for 2028, with the goal of maturing the IS technology entirely on the ground.

The IS is a high-strength, heat-resistant, 3-meter-diameter inflatable that forms part of the IHS, along with a flexible thermal protection system (F-TPS) [2]. It features an inverted tear-drop shape and a circular toroidal back-shell. This structure defines the aerodynamic profile of the ICARUS vehicle and is optimized for hypersonic re-entry, aerodynamic stability, manufacturing, and low leakage achieved using a single inflation volume. The material consists of an outer load-bearing high-strength woven fabric and an inner airtight gas bladder. To inflate the system, a Cool Gas Generator (CGG) developed by HDES is used. This in-house solution utilizes tuned porous grain propellant within a cylindrical cartridge that produces cool CO₂ when activated by a non-explosive igniter.

A stacked toroidal IS, as part of Inflatable Aerodynamic Decelerator (IAD) technology, was successfully demonstrated by NASA through the IRVE sub-orbital flights [3] and the LOFTID orbital re-entry mission in 2022 [4], achieving TRL 9. In Europe, similar progress has been made through the EFESTO [5] and EFESTO-2 [6] projects, culminating in the formation of

the ICARUS consortium. NASA’s solution featured a toroidal stack-up using Zylon with PTFE coating, a flexible TPS skirt, and pressurized nitrogen tanks derived from cold gas thruster heritage. EFESTO and EFESTO-2 focused on ground-based maturation and system design, including inflatable structure testing, simulations, and plasma wind tunnel testing of F-TPS material candidates.

2. INFLATABLE STRUCTURE DESIGN

The ICARUS IS design is developed from ATMOS experience designing, manufacturing, and attesting the Phoenix 1 IAD. It features a singular volume with a circular toroidal back-shell and an inverted tear-drop/conical interface to the nose-tip of the ICARUS vehicle. The manufacturing process utilizes fabric rolls with a nominal width of 1 m. To meet the required 3 m diameter, at least 10 segments are needed, as the 9.42 m circumference at the widest section allows for a maximum segment width of 0.942 m. These segments are joined at their overlap with preliminarily 25 mm wide high strength strap/belt, utilizing a double-felled seam that includes two parallel stitch-lines. Radial constraining patches, which do not contain a gas bladder, are added to facilitate the tear-drop shape of the inflatable.

The design iteration will follow a FEM and CFD loop (explained in sub-section 7.2) with varying the design space based on the parameterization of the structure to achieve best shape stability. This is validated through mechanical testing, representative breadboards, and qualification of a full-scale model under representative loads. Figure 1 shows an overview of the expected interfaces. The design parameterization and expected loads are addressed in sub-section 2.1 and 2.2 respectively.

Fig. 1: IS interface diagram and material stackup.

2.1. Design

Three system-level design inputs are relevant to the IS. First being geometric design, influenced by fabric manufacturing, aerothermodynamics constraints, and packaging on the sounding rocket. This results in certain design freedoms that are varied during the design and development process, while keeping within the prescribed margin. Second, mechanical and thermal loads are considered for material selection, structure construction, sewing technique, and sizing of segments and straps. Third, the availability of material and its intended functionality drive the design strongly. High level geometric parameterization and IS cross-section design are shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: IS section view and parameterization diagram. $R_{in,t}$ and $R_{out,t}$, inner and outer toroid radii respectively, are design freedoms of the parameterized space.

The following are current design constraints:

- Fabric interfaces are tangential to the IS contour.
- $D_{stowed} < 368 \text{ mm}$
- $D_{in} = 200 \text{ mm}$
- $D_{out} = 2993 \text{ mm}$ (-3.5 mm radius for F-TPS)
- $h_{max} = 1500 \text{ mm}$
- $\alpha = 30^\circ$ (cone half angle)
- $R_{nose} = 360 \text{ mm}$ (nose radius, not shown)

2.2. Loads

Loads on the deployed IS consist of pressure (internal and external), thermal loads, and deceleration load factor during descent. The peaks of pressure, thermal, and deceleration loads coincide and occur within a very short time frame of less than a minute. [1]

2.2.1. Pressure Loads

The IS is sized against an external total pressure of 8.8 kPa resulting from the 350 kg trajectory at the point of

peak dynamic pressure. To maintain a rigid structure that does not buckle under such loads and minimizes scalloping (concave bends into the segments) which result in overheating, the IS inflates to 10 kPa. Two initial inflation events take place, depicted in Figure 3, before reaching the entry interface point (EIP):

- Inflation Event 1: prior to apogee and after separation. IS unfolding and untangling begins, while the system is pressurized to 1 kPa in 60 s.
- Inflation Event 2: pressurization to 10 kPa before EIP but after apogee, over a period of 60 s.

At lower altitudes, after the peak loading of the re-entry vehicle, a total pressure balance occurs after the main investigation of the mission is completed. The IS is expected to collapse, no longer holding its intended shape.

Fig. 3: Inflation events and pressure over mission time.

2.2.2. Thermal Loads

Heating at the IS and F-TPS interface is with a delay from the incident heating-flux. A peak temperature of the IS outer layer is prescribed to 350 °C and on the order of 300 °C for several minutes for an orbital re-entry. [2]

2.2.3. Deceleration Loads

The load factor during the sub-orbital trajectory is expected to reach 11.4 g. This is considered in the FEM of the IS and its attachment to the rigid structure. [1]

3. MATERIAL SELECTION

The material candidates for the IS are drawn from high-temperature industrial applications and heritage components from similar missions. The IS is composed

of two main categories of materials: the outer load-bearing fabric and the inner airtight gas bladder. Additional components such as adhesives, sewing yarn, and meridional straps are critical for joining and structural interfacing. Load-bearing fabrics under consideration include para-aramid and Zylon, while the bladder materials range from high-temperature silicone laminates and polyimide tapes, to polyimide, silicone, or PTFE-impregnated fabrics. Adhesive selection depends on compatibility—silicone-based adhesive is used for polyimide, while a high-temperature glue is chosen for silicone materials. Structural strap options include para-aramid or Zylon, and the sewing yarn will be based on a high temperature aramid-steel yarn.

To determine the final material set, a selection process will be carried out starting with small-scale material samples for initial evaluation. This phase will be integrated with FEM simulations of the IS and physical testing using 2D breadboards to validate assumptions and performance. These efforts will converge toward a comprehensive thermo-mechanical characterization of all materials, which will inform final simulations and the overall structural sizing of the IS.

4. FIRST MATERIAL TESTING RESULTS

Initial material characterization focused on 2D lab testing under simplified loading conditions. Uniaxial tensile tests were performed on para-aramid and PTFE fabric to assess its elastic behavior, peak load capacity and strain at failure in both directions. These baseline results provide early insights into material performance under uniaxial tension and help build a preliminary structural analysis.

Further testing is planned to evaluate fabric behavior at elevated temperatures, which will better replicate the thermal environment experienced during re-entry. In addition, long-term material degradation is being investigated using atmospheric oven exposure, with specimens subjected to controlled aging cycles to assess mechanical property retention over time.

To complement mechanical testing, fabric flexibility and surface response are being quantified using partially the Kawabata Evaluation System (KES), which measures bending and shear properties. These parameters are critical for accurate modeling of the fabric’s behavior under large deformation and for capturing its nonlinear, orthotropic response in simulations.

4.1. Tensile Testing

Tensile tests were conducted to determine the preliminary material properties of several candidate materials. PTFE-coated glass fiber was evaluated as a potential bladder material, while para-aramid was considered both

as a load-bearing fabric and, when appropriately coated, taped, or laminated, as a potential gas bladder. The testing followed the DIN EN ISO 13934-1 standard, using samples measuring 50 mm × 200 mm, as shown in Figure 4. During the test campaign, each material was

Fig. 4: Tensile test stand and material.

subjected to five tensile tests in each principle direction, and the results were averaged. Figure 5 presents the average stress-strain results for both materials in the respective directions. Figure 5 highlights clear differ-

Fig. 5: Stress-Strain curve for Para Aramid and PTFE.

ences in the mechanical behavior of the PTFE-coated glass fiber compared to the para-aramid fabric. Para-aramid shows a steeper slope, indicating higher strength, reaching greater stress values at lower strains. In contrast, the PTFE-coated glass fiber exhibits a more gradual curve, reflecting lower tensile strength and greater flexibility. It suggest that para-aramid is more suitable for load-bearing or high-stress applications.

4.2. Leakage Testing

Leakage tests were conducted on fabric samples measuring 100 mm × 100 mm, clamped to the side of a sealed chamber with a volume of 0.056 m³. Each sample exposed an effective fabric area of 64 cm² to the internal over-pressure. The procedure involved pressurizing the chamber to 5.6 kPa with air using a digital regulator, after which the enclosure was isolated by closing a manual valve. The pressure drop was then measured over time

to assess leakage. This test was repeated for five samples of each material to ensure consistency and repeatability of the results. The test setup is shown in Figure 6, where the pressurized container was checked for leakages prior to each test. Tested materials include PTFE-coated glass fiber, polyimide taped para-aramid, and a 0.3 mm high temperature silicone laminated para-aramid.

Fig. 6: Leakage test setup.

Leakage testing results, presented in Figure 7, demonstrate good reproducibility across all five samples for each test, with consistent values relative to the mean leakage rate. Among the tested materials, silicone-laminated para-aramid exhibited the lowest leakage, indicated by the slowest pressure drop over time. This can be attributed to the material’s broader, continuous silicone rolls—typically up to 1.5 m wide—which avoid the overlaps required by narrower polyimide tape (0.1 m wide). Additionally, silicone-laminated para-aramid is more flexible than PTFE-coated glass fiber, further contributing to its sealing performance since the coated glass fiber may have produced small tears and holes while handling.

Some leakage was still observed in all samples, primarily due to the challenge of clamping the fabrics tightly enough to form a completely airtight seal. Moving forward, testing with CO₂ will be essential to more accurately assess which bladder material performs best under realistic operational conditions. Furthermore, an improvement of the test stand is planned to best support subsequent testing campaigns.

Fig. 7: Leakage test results.

5. IS "PILLOW" BREADBOARD

The "Pillow" breadboard serves as a small-scale prototype of the inflatable structure. It features an elliptical (or near-elliptical) cross-sectional shape, incorporates at least two internal constraining patches, and is designed to be folded and unfolded using a reproducible procedure. It enables the preliminary testing of sensor integration and interfacing, development of inflation line interfaces, and the evaluation of initial sewing techniques on a representative inflatable model that is quickly producible from a relatively small amount of material. As the development of the ICARUS IS progresses, the Pillow breadboard provides a platform for rapid iteration, allowing new design concepts and improvements to be tested and validated efficiently.

The first iteration of the breadboard was sewn from para-aramid fabric, with polyimide tape used to create a sealed gas bladder. Intended as the first inflatable manufactured for the ICARUS consortium by ATMOS, this version includes two un-taped internal constraining patches. The prototype measures 450 mm in length and has a total internal volume of 13.6 liters. Figure 8 illustrates both the cross-sectional parametrization and the resulting 3D geometry of the breadboard. A minimum diameter of 25 mm was selected, to de-risk application in other sub-scale IS breadboards with an approximate diameter of 0.5 m. This initial trial demonstrated that sewing such tight radii is feasible using the chosen materials and fabrication techniques. In Figure 9, the man-

Fig. 8: Cross-section of the parameterized pillow breadboard (top), and the resultant 3D shape with the closing seam, interfaces, and constraining patches shown (bottom).

ufacturing and first inflation of the pillow is shown. Two 3D-printed prototype inflation interfaces are used for

Fig. 9: Pillow breadboard showing constraining patches (a), inflation and pressure measurement interfaces (b), deflated breadboard (c), and inflated breadboard (d).

inflation and pressure measurement respectively. Pressurized air is used for inflation, along with a differential pressure regulator for a set over-pressure. In this first iterations, seams were not sealed, prioritizing gaining quick experience in manufacturing and interfacing. The 25 mm radii proved to be difficult to sew, and are beyond the limit when sewing an entire inflatable structure (where the support equipment used to hold the already finished segments of the IS limits minimum radius).

A peak overpressure of 2.2 kPa was recorded within the structure. Due to unsealed seams and the still-unoptimized manufacturing of the IS, the permeability remained too high, preventing higher pressures from being reached. Moving forward, the breadboard will be enlarged to accommodate the CGGs, with initial inflation achieving an overpressure of 1 kPa. While minimal radii of 25 mm are feasible, they will only be used when necessary, with larger radii preferred in future iterations. Additional testing will also explore alternative material candidates, such as Para-Aramid combined with a laminated silicone bladder.

6. ICARUS INFLATION SYSTEM

For IS inflation, different options are available. These include pressurized gas systems, evaporating solids or liquids, and hot or cool gas generators. Important considerations in the selection of the inflation system are:

- Inflation shall be completed in few minutes.
- Inflation shall be controlled or predictable.
- Thermal impact on the structure shall be limited.
- Safety before and during flight, and after landing.
- CGGs shall be European sourced as much as possible.

Given the above criteria, inflation methods were evaluated and ruled out. Evaporating fluid systems are too slow to be effective. Pressurized gas tanks, while efficient in volume, are complex and pose safety risks due to high pressures, particularly during landing. Hot gas generators, being pyrotechnic, produce high temperatures that risk damaging the structure. Cool Gas Generator (CGG) technology performs well across all criteria. Nitrogen-based systems offer high performance but involve toxic propellants and reactive byproducts. CO₂-based systems are safer, lower cost, and meet performance needs. Since CGGs consists of a small fraction of the ICARUS vehicle’s mass, and safety and cost are priorities, a CO₂-based CGG was selected for the inflation system.

A CGG is a solid propellant rocket motor that, after ignition with a small igniter, produces a nearly pure gas at ambient temperature. This is due to the porous propellant that has been specially modified for this application. As the reaction in the propellant is designed to produce a pure gas, 50%-60% of the propellant mass remains in the CGG. [7] provides a more detailed description of the CO₂ CGG.

For the two-stage IS inflation, small CGGs will each deliver 20 nl of CO₂ gas for the initial inflation, then larger CGGs will deliver 250 nl each and achieve full inflation. Two CGGs of each type have been chosen to allow a balanced placement in the confined space of the ICARUS vehicle main structure, with stainless steel selected as the primary construction material. This builds a level of redundancy in the system. To achieve as much commonality as possible between the two CGGs, both have the same length at 290 mm, but different diameters. Due to this difference, the two CGGs have been named “El Flaco” and “El Gordo” with Laurel and Hardy in mind. The use of stainless steel and the strategic positioning of the CGGs near the nose tip of the ICARUS vehicle also contribute to better stability during inflation, optimizing the system’s performance. Table 1 gives an overview of the main CGG characteristics. A modular

Table 1: “El Flaco” and “El Gordo” CGG properties.

Property	El Flaco	El Gordo
CO ₂ gas production	20 nl (39 g)	250 nl (490 g)
CGG mass	425 g	2500 g
CGG diameter	23 mm	78 mm
Gas production time	60 s	60 s

test stand, shown in Figure 10, was designed to facilitate grain development. It accommodates various tube lengths and diameters, enabling rapid testing of different configurations. Time series measurements of the flow

from the CGG is possible. By March 2025, the first

Fig. 10: “El Flaco” CGG during testing in Noordwijk.

test with the grains of “El Flaco” was successfully completed, and the CGG characteristics were found to be close to predictions. Figure 11 shows that over 18 nl of CO₂ gas were released during a 60-second period by the “El Flaco” CGG after ignition. The flat line indicate the overflow limit of the available flow-rate sensor, Further testing is ongoing to tune and build confidence in the system and to subsequently test “El Gordo” and design flight-suitable casings.

Fig. 11: Flow as a function of time graph of an “El Flaco” CGG test using the test stand shown in Figure 10.

7. IS NUMERICAL SIMULATION

To ensure reliable deployment and operation of the inflatable structure, numerical structural analysis are conducted to evaluate its mechanical response during inflation. In this preliminary phase, the study focuses specifically on the structure’s stress distribution, deformation behavior, and stability under the combined effects of internal inflation pressure and external aerodynamic loads. It also aims to give valuable feedback on different materials, to help determine the most suitable one.

Due to the large deformations, nonlinear material behavior, and complex contact interactions intrinsic to inflatable systems, a nonlinear finite element approach is required to capture the relevant physical phenomena with

sufficient fidelity. The simulations have been performed using RADIOSS by Altair, which is appropriate for non-linear simulation.

7.1. Model Description

The preliminary simulation is based on a simplified structural model of the IS, designed to capture its baseline mechanical response during inflation and under external loading. To capture key mechanical effects, the simulation incorporates the inflatable structure, the externally positioned structural straps to constrain deformation, the internal patches for local reinforcement, and a rigid body to represent the equipment onboard.

Fig. 12: Inflatable Structure mesh.

Simulation of the inflatable structure follows the following conditions:

- Simulation run time: 300 ms
- Internal overpressure: 10k Pa
- ONERA CFD 350 kg trajectory pressure map [8]
- Perfectly sealed volume
- No thermal load assumed
- IS material from para-aramid

A key parameter in the simulation is the modeling of the fabric, as it significantly influences the response of the inflatable system. Due to the flexible, anisotropic, and nonlinear nature of fabrics, their accurate representation is essential for capturing realistic deformation and stress distributions. In RADIOSS, two primary material models are available for this purpose:

- LAW 19 defines elastic orthotropic fabric
- LAW 58 defines hyperelastic anisotropic fabric

In the current simulation phase, the fabric material is modeled using Law 19, based on uniaxial tensile test data presented in Figure 5. This model offers a simplified representation of the fabric’s nonlinear stress-strain behavior

and is suitable for preliminary analyses focused on capturing general deformation trends and identifying critical loading zones. However, Law 19 does not account for the orthotropic properties or specific behavior inherent to woven technical textiles.

As the material characterization campaign progresses the simulation approach will transition to Law 58. This model allows the inclusion of orthotropic stiffness, wrinkling behavior, and strain-rate sensitivity. By incorporating additional experimental data, Law 58 will enable a more accurate and physically representative simulation of the material performance under complex loading conditions.

7.2. Preliminary Result

Initial simulations have provided insights into the structural behavior of the inflatable structure. As shown in Figure 13, stress concentrations are primarily located near the strap attachment regions and at the center of the internal constraining patches. Figure 14 indicates

Fig. 13: Stress Preliminary Result.

that the highest strain levels occur in the patches’ central zones and regions between adjacent straps. These findings highlight the importance of reinforcing critical areas to ensure structural integrity during deployment and operation. From the first analysis, reinforcement will be necessary in the patch regions, where higher stress concentrations appear.

These results feed into a CFD-FEM iterative loop aimed at improving both structural integrity and aerodynamic accuracy. Due to the tear-drop shape of the inflatable structure, numerical modeling is essential. By linking FEM with CFD, it is possible to account for deformation-driven effects like shape deflection, which influence aerodynamics and thermal loads. The FEM output provides a more realistic geometry for the CFD, and this cycle is repeated until convergence, enabling a structurally and aerodynamically optimized design.

Fig. 14: Strain Preliminary Result.

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- <https://www.he-icarus-project.eu/>
- <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101134997>

Fig. 15: ICARUS project logo.

9. OUTLOOK

A full material characterization will take place to feed models and simulations, along with the further development of small breadboards such as the pillow. Simulations will be improved, particularly focusing on refining the implementation of LAW 58 for more accurate material modeling. The design loop incorporating a finite element (FE) parametric study will be established to optimize structural performance. Additionally, a coupled FE-CFD shape-morphing study will be conducted to obtain an optimized design.

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